

Press Release #4
Thursday 28th, 2026

COcyber Final Conference to address Europe's need for a unified cyber shield across borders

Discussions will focus on cross-border collaboration, protecting democratic processes, translating policy into practice, and advancing dual-use cyber innovation.

Brussels, Belgium. The [COcyber](#) project will host its Final Conference, [A Unified Response to Multiple Threats: Building Europe's Cyber Shield Across Borders](#), on **25 June 2026** at the Residence Palace in Brussels.

As cyber threats continue to evolve in scale and complexity, strengthening cooperation across borders has become an urgent priority for Europe. The conference will bring together policymakers, practitioners, researchers and innovators to **assess the current state of European cybersecurity cooperation** and identify practical pathways toward stronger collective action.

The programme will open with *Outpacing the Threat: Why Europe Needs a Unified Cyber Shield and How to Build It*, a panel exploring the **challenges, gaps and opportunities** shaping cross-border cybersecurity collaboration.

Two parallel sessions will follow. *Need for Speed: From Policy to Practice in Strengthening Europe's Cyber Posture* will **examine how policy ambition can be translated into operational reality**. *Safeguarding Democracy in the Digital Age: A Unified European Response to Cyber Threats* will focus on **protecting democratic processes**, public trust, essential services and institutions against emerging cyber risks

The afternoon panel, *Dual Use, Single Vision: Rethinking Cyber Innovation*, will explore the **intersection of civilian and defence** cybersecurity and discuss how innovation can strengthen Europe's resilience, competitiveness and long-term security.

The COcyber Final Conference will present the project's findings, place them in dialogue with the broader expert community, and contribute to ongoing efforts **toward a more coordinated European approach to cyber resilience**.

[Register now](#) to join the discussion in Brussels and connect with stakeholders working across cybersecurity, policy, research and the innovation ecosystem.

25 JUNE 2026

9:00 am - 17:00 pm CET
Residence Palace
Brussels

A Unified Response to Multiple Threats: Building Europe's Cyber Shield Across Borders

FINAL CONFERENCE

Don't miss it

ECCC
EUROPEAN CYBERSECURITY
COMPETENCE CENTRE

Funded by
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About COcyber: [COcyber](#) is an ambitious two-year EU-funded initiative launched in July 2024 to strengthen exchange, coordination, and collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity communities across Europe. Led by 28DIGITAL and involving nine European organisations, the project delivers practical tools, policy frameworks, and a trusted online platform to bridge the gap between sectors and support a unified response to evolving cyber threats.

Follow COcyber on [LinkedIn](#) and [Bluesky](#) - stay tuned for further developments in this collaborative ecosystem!

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